

HALOGENATION. PART XXI. DIRECT REPLACEMENT OF AROMATIC SULPHONIC GROUPS BY CHLORINE AND BROMINE ATOMS.

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In about 50 aromatic hydrocarbons and their derivatives, the sulphonic group or groups have been replaced by chlorine and bromine atoms by heating strongly the sulphonic acid derivatives or their sodium salts with cupric chloride and cupric bromide respectively.

Sulphonic groups in aromatic compounds are readily replaced by hydroxyl and cyanogen groups by fusing sulphonic acid derivatives with alkali hydroxides and alkali cyanides respectively. No direct replacement of sulphonic groups in aromatic compounds by chlorine or bromine atoms takes place. With a view to replacing the sulphonic group by chlorine atom in benzene sulphonic acid or its sodium salt, the latter has been fused in a glass or copper flask with the chlorides of sodium, potassium, silver, magnesium, lead, zinc, iron (ferric), chromium and copper (both cuprous and cupric).

It is only when sulphonic acid derivatives of aromatic hydrocarbons or of some of their derivatives are heated strongly with copper chloride and bromide (both cupric and cuprous) that sulphonic groups are replaced by chlorine and bromine atoms and chloro and bromo compounds are obtained.

This method has been extended to a number of aromatic sulphonic acid derivatives or their salts or some of their nuclear substituted derivatives, resulting in the formation of the corresponding halogen compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A weighed quantity of the sulphonic acid or its sodium salt was mixed thoroughly with cupric chloride or bromide and the mixture heated strongly over a naked flame for about 2½ hours in a copper distilling flask provided with a condenser and a receiver. In several cases a brisk evolution of sulphur dioxide took place. The products collected in the receiver were ordinarily

The experiments on benzene sulphonic acid alone have been carried with Mr. Subramaniam and the rest of the experiments have been conducted with Mr. Parekh.

coloured, greenish brown in the case of copper chloride and reddish brown in the case of copper bromide. In some cases, the products were obtained as liquids and in others they were partly liquid and partly solid. The products were separated, washed, dried and distilled or crystallised as the case may be and then identified. The yields of the pure halogen compounds obtained from 25 g. of the following sulphonic acids with CuCl_2 or CuBr_2 (quantities varying roughly from 20-25 g.) are summarised below.

Substances used.	Products with yield.
Benzene-sulphonic acid or its Na-salt	... Chlorobenzene (3 g.)
Benzene-sulphonic acid or its Na-salt	... Bromobenzene (4.25 g.)
Benzene-disulphonic acid	... <i>m</i> -Dibromobenzene (5.1 g.)
<i>o</i> -Bromobenzene-sulphonic acid	... 1-Bromo-2-chlorobenzene (4.3 g.)
<i>o</i> -Bromobenzene-sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Dibromobenzene (4.3 g.)
2 : 5-Dichlorobenzene-sulphonic acid	... 1 : 2 : 5-Trichlorobenzene (4.1 g.)
2 : 5-Dichlorobenzene-sulphonic acid	... 2 : 5-Dichlorobenzene sulphobromide (1.5 g.) + 1-bromo-2:5-dichlorobenzene (1.4 g.)
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene-sulphonic acid	... <i>m</i> -Nitrochlorobenzene (4.4 g.)
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene-sulphonic acid	... <i>m</i> -Nitrobromobenzene (4.1 g.)
3 : 4-Dichlorobenzene-sulphonic acid	... 1 : 3 : 4-Trichlorobenzene (7.9 g.)
2 : 4-Dichlorobenzene-sulphonic acid	... 1-Bromo-3 : 4-dichlorobenzene (6.8 g.)
<i>p</i> -Toluene-sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene (8.1 g.)
<i>p</i> -Toluene-sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Bromotoluene (8.4 g.)
<i>o</i> -Toluene-sulphonic acid	.. <i>o</i> -Chlorotoluene (8.0 g.)
<i>o</i> -Toluene-sulphonic acid	.. <i>o</i> -Bromotoluene (8.3 g.)
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene-sulphonic acid	. 4-Nitro-2-chlorotoluene (6.5 g.)
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene-sulphonic acid	.. 4-Nitro-2-bromotoluene (3.5 g.)
<i>o</i> -Xylene-sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>o</i> -xylene (7.6 g.)
<i>o</i> -Xylene-sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Bromo- <i>o</i> -xylene (7.3 g.)
<i>m</i> -Xylene-sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>m</i> -xylene (9.1 g.)
<i>m</i> -Xylene-sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Bromo- <i>m</i> -xylene (8.1 g.)
<i>p</i> -Xylene-sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Chloro- <i>p</i> -xylene (8.1 g.)
<i>p</i> -Xylene-sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Bromo- <i>p</i> -xylene (8 g.)
Mesitylene-sulphonic acid	... Chloromesitylene (7.2 g.)
Mesitylene-sulphonic acid	... Bromomesitylene (7.2 g.)
Diphenyl- <i>p</i> -sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Chlorodiphenyl (2.5 g.)
Diphenyl- <i>p</i> -sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Bromodiphenyl (2.5 g.)
Naphthalene-1-sulphonic acid	... 1-Chloronaphthalene (7.1 g.)
Naphthalene-1-sulphonic acid	... 1-Bromonaphthalene (4.1 g.)

Substance used	Products with yield.
Naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid	... 2-Chloronaphthalene (1.1 g.)
Naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid	... 2-Bromonaphthalene (1.2 g.)
Naphthalene-1: 5-disulphonic acid	... 1: 5-Dichloronaphthalene (2.4 g.)
Naphthalene-1: 5-disulphonic acid	... 1: 5-Dibromonaphthalene (3.7 g.)
Naphthalene-2: 7-disulphonic acid	... 2: 7-Dichloronaphthalene (3.1 g.)
Naphthalene-2: 7-disulphonic acid	... 2: 7-Dibromonaphthalene (4.6 g.)
1-Naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid	... 4-Chloro-1-naphthylamine (3.2 g.)
1-Naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid	... 4-Bromo-1-naphthylamine (3.4 g.)
2-Naphthylamine-6: 8-disulphonic acid	... 6: 8-Dichloro-2-naphthylamine (1.8 g.)
2-Naphthylamine-6: 8-disulphonic acid	... 6: 8-Dibromo-2-naphthylamine (1.1 g.)
2-Naphthylamine-4: 8-disulphonic acid	... 4: 8-Dichloro-2-naphthylamine (2.1 g.)
2-Naphthylamine-4: 8-disulphonic acid	... 4: 8-Dibromo-2-naphthylamine (2.4 g.)
<i>o</i> -Toluidine-4: 5-disulphonic acid	... 4: 5-Dichloro- <i>o</i> -toluidine (1.1 g.)
<i>o</i> -Toluidine-4: 5-disulphonic acid	... 4: 5-Dibromo- <i>o</i> -toluidine (1.2 g.)
Phenol- <i>o</i> -sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Chlorophenol (2.5 g.)
Phenol- <i>o</i> -sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Bromophenol (2.6 g.)
2-Naphthol-6-sulphonic acid	... 6-Chloro-2-naphthol (2.8 g.)
Cyanobenzene- <i>p</i> -sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzonitrile (6.5 g.)
Cyanobenzene- <i>p</i> -sulphonic acid	... <i>p</i> -Bromobenzonitrile (6.9 g.)
Benzoic acid-sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid (7.8 g.)
Benzoic acid-sulphonic acid	... <i>o</i> -Bromobenzoic acid (7.8 g.)

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